

STAGES OF HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE FRUITS OF ORAL LITERATURE

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Summary. *The article examines the historical development stages of the fruits of oral folk literature in a consistent and systematic manner. It is shown that oral folk literature, starting from the stage of mythological thinking, went through epic and lyrical periods of development, and then evolved to the modern stage by interacting with written literature. In the initial stage, the attitude of man to nature was expressed through myths, legends and beliefs, and in the epic stage, the ideas of heroism, historical memory and national identity were formed through the creation of epics.*

In the Middle Ages, the development of lyrical genres - bayati, goshma, garayli, layla and aghi - strengthened the artistic expression of the inner world of man, and the art of ashug was formed as the pinnacle of oral poetry. In the modern era, the recording and scientific study of folklore led to the systematization of genres, and in the modern era, although technological development has changed the forms of dissemination of oral literature, it has preserved its essence.

As a result, the fruits of oral folk literature act as the main carriers of the people's historical memory, spiritual values, and national identity, and their study is of great importance in ensuring cultural continuity.

Keywords: *folklore, epic, ashug art, national memory, genre, stages of development*

Introduction. Oral folk literature is one of the oldest and richest creative fields, reflecting the spiritual memory, worldview and aesthetic taste of each people. This literature was transmitted orally from generation to generation for centuries before being put into written form, embodying the lifestyle, system of thought and historical destiny of the people. The fruits of oral folk literature – that is, its genres and poetic forms – have changed, enriched and evolved in parallel with the socio-cultural development of society in the process of historical development. In this regard, studying the stages of its development is of great importance both from the point of view of folklore studies and national-cultural history in general.

The initial stage of development of oral folk literature is associated with mythological thinking. During this period, since man could not yet explain the laws of nature scientifically, he tried to understand it through myths, beliefs and symbolic images. The sun, moon, water, earth, mountains and other elements of nature were sanctified and formed the basis of the mythological system. The legends and tales that emerged at this stage were more cosmogonic, totemic and animistic in nature. There was an inseparable connection between man and nature, and this connection was reflected in artistic creativity. Thus, the first fruits of oral folk literature emerged as a product of mythological thought.

The next stage is characterized by the formation of epic thinking. During this period, man begins to artistically express not only nature, but also social relations, tribal and tribal life, events of struggle and heroism. Epics are the most striking example of this stage. *Epic creation, in addition to being an artistic form of the collective memory of the people, plays an important role in the formation of national identity* (6, p. 18). Here, hero images are idealized, values such as justice, courage, patriotism are brought to the fore. Epics do not only serve the purpose of entertainment, but also act as a means of transmitting the historical experience and moral ideals of the people to future generations.

During the Middle Ages, the fruits of oral folk literature became even richer and entered a new qualitative stage. At this stage, the development of lyrical genres attracted special attention. A person began to express his inner world, feelings such as love, longing, joy and sadness in a more subtle and

poetic way. Bayati, goshmash, gerayli, aghi, layla and okshama became widespread as the main poetic forms of this period. Bayati in particular stood out as a concise and profound form of expression of folk wisdom. Despite the four-line structure, bayati contained great life experience and philosophical thought.

The formation and development of ashug art at this stage is considered one of the pinnacles of oral folk literature. Ashugs, reciting poetry accompanied by saz, created unique examples of art that combined both epic and lyrical traditions. They acted not only as artists, but also as spokesmen, bearers of memory, and spiritual leaders of the people. *Ashug creativity led to the further enrichment of oral literature in terms of genre and form* (5, p.21).

In the new period, oral folk literature enters into interaction with written literature and gains new directions of development. During this period, the process of collecting, recording and scientifically studying folklore samples begins. The interaction between genres intensifies, some oral forms pass into written literature and acquire new content. At the same time, small genres such as proverbs, sayings, riddles retain their function as an integral part of everyday life. This stage can be characterized as a period of synthesis of oral and written literature.

In modern times, the fruits of oral folk literature are being transformed in accordance with new social and technological conditions. *Globalization, the development of information technologies and the spread of mass communication media have affected the forms of transmission of folklore* (3, p. 17). Along with the traditional oral form of transmission, folklore samples are now also being preserved in written, audio-visual and digital media. However, the main essence of oral folk literature - collective creativity, preservation of national memory and transmission of spiritual values - remains unchanged.

All these stages show that the fruits of oral folk literature are not just artistic forms, but also a mirror of the historical development, worldview and cultural evolution of the people. This path of development, starting from mythological thought to epic and lyrical peaks, and from there to the stage of modern transformation, is a clear indicator of the spiritual richness of the people. The study, preservation and transmission of this heritage to future generations is of great importance in terms of ensuring national identity and cultural continuity.

REFERENCES

1. Akhundov A. Azerbaijani fairy tales. In five volumes. Volume IV. Baku, Sharq-Garb, -336 p.
2. Azerbaijani bayats. Baku. Science and education. 2022 -316 p.
3. Anthology of Azerbaijani Folklore. Book XII. (Zangezour folklore). Baku, Sada, 2005, -428 p.
4. Collection of Azerbaijani Folklore. Volume XX. Epics (Book X). Baku, Nurlan, 2010, -392 p.
5. Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore, Book II (Iraqi-Turkmen folklore). Baku, Nurlan, 2009, -436 p.
6. Anthology of Azerbaijani Folklore. Book VIII (Aghbaba folklore), Baku, Sada, 2003, .
7. The book of Dede Gorgud (Vatican copy). Baku. Khan. 2018. -288 p.
8. Hans Christian Anderson. Fairy tales. Baku. Ondar. 2004, -160 p.
9. Kitabi-Dade Gorgud. Baku, Ondar, 2004, -376 p.
10. Garayev S. Guliyev H. Azerbaijani fairy tales: Images and functions. Baku. Savad. 2021. -456 p.